

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MILITARY COMPONENT IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract. This article highlights the importance of teaching English to cadets of military educational institutions.

Key words: English, military affairs, science, interdisciplinarity, communication.

РЕАЛИЗАЦИЯ ВОЕННОГО КОМПОНЕНТА НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. В данной статье освещается важность преподавания английского языка курсантам военно-учебных заведений.

Ключевые слова: Английский язык, военное дело, наука, междисциплинарность, общение.

INTRODUCTION

English occupies a special place among a number of other academic disciplines. Its specificity as a subject lies in the fact that through its study, students not only acquire knowledge, but also acquire the skills and abilities to use it as a means of communication, a means of obtaining new information. Taking into account the transition to modern educational standards and the specifics of military educational institutions, teaching English gives teachers ample opportunities to instill patriotism and citizenship. A lot of such opportunities are facilitated by the communicative essence of the discipline, its focus on the study of the life, traditions and language of another people.

The study of any foreign culture through the study of the language of another country is possible only with the formed cultural and national base of the native language. Only in this case, the knowledge obtained through a foreign language is perceived through the prism of knowledge based on a deep understanding of the native culture. Acquaintance with the realities of English-speaking countries means the need to study state symbols, history, geography, culture by means of the studied foreign language. It must be understood that it is impossible to separate the moral and historical principles.

The history of one's state, key events and exploits of heroic compatriots are the most fruitful substrate for the development of patriotism. Thus, the formation of historical consciousness entails the simultaneous strengthening of the moral ideals and patriotic feelings of students, their love for the Motherland.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Intercultural communication should a priori be realized on the basis of national culture, the heritage of one's own people, and the culture of one's native land. At the same time, the wider the system of own knowledge about the native culture, which the student operates with, the more actively and productively he studies the culture of another state. The role of a foreign language teacher is to instill in students an international spirit, respect for the rights and freedoms of the individual, high morality and tolerance, respect for the culture, traditions and language of other peoples, taking into account Russian realities.

The development of foreign language speech activity of students is a purposeful process of both the formation and transformation of speech activity, during which the development of speech actions leads to the formation of speech skills, which, in turn, improves the quality of education of cadets. One of the main tasks of the teacher is to create conditions for the self-development of each student. One of these conditions is the properly organized independent work of students in the study of a foreign language, since deep, solid knowledge and stable skills can only be acquired as a result of independent work.

It is important to develop in cadets the ability to formulate the main goals of the work performed; analyze the situation and draw conclusions, abstract the content and highlight the essential; arrange information in the form of an abstract or report; plan independent work, use modern reference sources; exercise self-control over work, objectively evaluate the result, and so on.

The effective organization of independent work of students, of course, should be based on the basis of methodological support: for example, computer programs for independent work, textbooks that include texts for independent reading, sections on scientific annotation and abstracting of specialized literature, collections of exercises and grammar tests for self-control and so on.

Properly organized independent work of students makes it possible to eliminate the orientation towards the "average" student in the learning process, increases the interest in achieving better results in educational activities for greater professional returns in the future. Cadets acquire the ability to purposefully shape themselves as a creative person, manage their own activities and behavior.

Immersion of a student in a technical and linguistic environment undoubtedly contributes to the intensification of the process of teaching a foreign language. The language of the student today is saturated with scientific, technical and special military terms, which he gets acquainted with in the process of training in his special disciplines and quite clearly understands their meaning. This kind of knowledge must be used in the process of teaching foreign languages, especially since many of these special words are international. These words can act as supports in the process of immersion in the techno-linguistic environment, on the one hand, and on the other hand, they can contribute to the integration of special disciplines and teaching a foreign language to future specialists.

CONCLUSION

Interdisciplinary connections play an important role in teaching a foreign language and are closely interconnected with the life experience that students have at the time of training and which is formed in them in the process of mastering a specialty. In this case, the question arises of defining common problems and, on the basis of existing knowledge, combining the vision of the problem and possible options for solving it in a foreign language. Since the achievement of successful learning outcomes, including a foreign language, depends to a decisive extent on the direction, degree of independence, manifestation of creative abilities and internal activity of students, the nature of their activities, then these factors should serve as an important criterion for choosing the method that the teacher achieves in the process of learning the tasks assigned to them. Taking into account and application by the teacher of higher education of such aspects of teaching as the life experience of students, immersion in the techno-linguistic environment, the use of

interdisciplinary connections, is aimed at enhancing the language training of future military specialists.

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